

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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KEYWORDS

entrepreneurship, business,
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ABSTRACT

In this article, small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan are important factors in the development of the economy, increasing the employment and income of the population. In recent years, we can see the decisions and decrees of the President in order to support this industry from all sides.

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O'ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI

KALIT SO'ZLAR:

tadbirkorlik, biznes, bozor mexanizmlari, kichik biznes

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, aholi bandligi va daromadlarini oshirishda muhim omillar keltirib o'tiladi. Ushbu sohani har taraflama qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida oxirgi yillarda Prezidentimizning qaror va farmonlarini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Tadbirkorlik (tadbirkorlik faoliyati bu- iqtisodiy foydadir) — o'z tavakkalchiligi ostida amalga oshiriladigan, mulkka egalik qilish, tovarlarni sotish, ishlarni bajarish yoki xizmatlar ko'rsatishdan muntazam ravishda daromad olishga qaratilgan mustaqil faoliyat sanaladi. Tadbirkorlik faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxslar, agar qonun hujjatlarida boshqacha tartib nazarda tutilgan bo'lmasa, qonun hujjatlarida belgilangan tartibda ushbu lavozimda ro'yxatdan o'tkazilishi kerak.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznesning rivojlanishdagi mavjud muammolarning yechimini topish va 2017-2021 yillarda istiqbollashtirilayotgan parametrlarni ta'minlash, ushbu sohada tadbirkorlik faolligini oshirishning yo'nalishlarini aniqlash va ular chora- tadbirlarni belgilashni talab etadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida Biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- kichik biznesning huquqiy-me'yoriy va tashkiliy asoslarini iqtisodiyotda turli omillar ta'sirida ro'y berayotgan o'zgarishlarga mos ravishda uzluksiz takomillashtirib borish;

- davlat tomonidan biznes va huquqiy tadbirkorlikni qo'llab- quvvatlash mexanizmlarini samaradorligini oshirish, bu borada xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasidagi yangi mexanizmlarni mavjud sharoitlarga moslashtirganholda amaliyotga qo'llash;

- kichik biznesning innovasiya negizida rivojlanishini ta'minlash borasida chora – tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish;

- kichik biznesni moliyaviy jihatdan ta'minlash mavjud mexanizmlar samaradorligini oshirish va moliyalashtirishning yangi manbalarini harakatga keltirish negizida qulay investisiya muhitini yaratish;

- kichik biznesda ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishning moddiy ta'minotini takomillashtirish;

- kichik biznesni tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyat mexanizmlarini takomil- lashtirish;

- biznessohasi uchun malakali raqobatbardosh kadrlarni tayyorlash;

- kichik biznesda kooperasiyani chuqurlashtirish.

O'zbekistonda kichik korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimining takomillashtirilishi kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikka xizmat ko'rsatadigan banklar,

fondlar, investiyalar va sug`urta tashkilotlarining faoliyatlarini rag`batlantirish yo`nalishida olib borilishi lozim. Xorijiy mamlakatlardagi kabi O`zbekiston Respublikasida ham agar korxonalar ustuvor davlat dasturida (yangi texnikani yaratish, uzoq hududlarni rivojlantirish va boshqalar) qatnashayotgan bo`lsa, imtiyozli qarzlar olishi mumkin. Bunda foizning eng kam me`yori va qarzni uzishda uzoq muddat berilishi – qarz berishdagi asosiy shartlardandir.

Kichik korxonalar faoliyatiga oldindan ko`rib bo`lmaydigan xilma-xil xatarli vaziyatlar katta ta`sir ko`rsatadi, kon`yunkturaning keskin o`zgarib ketishi, mijozlarning to`lovga qodir bo`lmay qolishi, tabiiy ofatlar ularni tang ahvolga tushirib qo`yadi. Shu sababli rivojlangan mamlakatlarda sug`urtalar tizimi yaxshi yo`lga qo`yilgan. Bizning mamlakatimizda ham sug`urtalar barpo etilishi zarur. Bu tizim kichik korxonalarni rivojlantirishda (ayniqsa, tijorat xatarlari katta bo`lgan sohalarda) qulay sharoitlarni kafolatlashi, o`ziniki bo`lgan yoki qarz olingan kapital bilan tavakkal qilib ish boshlagan tadbirkorlarga ishonch va zarur barqarorlikni yaratishi kerak.

Ma`lumki, respublikada mehnatga layoqatli aholining 65 foizidan ortiq qismi qishloqlarda yashaydi. Bu qishloq joylarda tadbirkorlikning rivoji uchun juda katta imkoniyatlar mavjudligini ko`rsatadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, qishloq xo`jaligi ishlab chiqarishida band bo`lgan ortiqcha ishchi kuchlarini xizmat ko`rsatish, qayta ishlash va shu kabi yo`nalishlarga qayta taqsimlash kerak. Qishloqda tadbirkorlikni, uning kichik biznes shakllarini rivojlantirish bilan bog`liq turli boshqaruv pog`onalarida tashkiliy-iqtisodiy masalalarni hal etish ustuvor masalalar qatoriga kiradi.

Bu maqsadlarni amalga oshirish uchun mamlakatimiz miqyosida quyidagi masalalarni hal qilish lozim:

- bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida ishlash uchun kadrlar tayyorlash va ularning malakasini oshirish;
- hududlarda haqiqiy tadbirkorlik muhitini yaratish;
- kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyaviy jihatdan qo`llab-quvvatlash; - kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning huquqiy bazasini mustahkamlash;
- kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni texnologik jihozlar bilan ta`minlashni qo`llab-quvvatlash;
- islohotlar natijalarini reklama va axborot xizmati vositalari orqali keng ommaga etkazish.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, O`zbekistonda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirar ekanmiz, avvalambor xalqimizni kambag`allikdan chiqaramiz va ishsizlikni kamaytiramiz. Hozirgi kunga muxtaram Prezidentimiz shu sohada faoliyat yuritayotgan har bir tadbirkorga juda ko`plab imkoniyatlar ochib bermoqda.

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